

Fitting of data: JBW-NP-P-V7 2021-02-18_08-10-08
 $0.0201 \leq q \text{ (nm}^{-1}\text{)} \leq 24$
 Active parameters: 1, ranges: 1
 Background level: 0.123 ± 0.000865
 (Scaling factor: $2.77\text{e}+33 \pm 4.04\text{e}+31$)
 Timing: 10 repetitions of 109 ± 117 seconds

Range $1.500\text{e}-10$ to $1.500\text{e}-07$, vol-weighted
 totalValue: $2.076\text{e}-04 \pm 2.179\text{e}-07$
 mean: $3.524\text{e}-09 \pm 6.450\text{e}-12$
 variance: $9.746\text{e}-19 \pm 6.405\text{e}-20$
 skew: $4.428\text{e}+00 \pm 4.526\text{e}-01$
 kurtosis: $4.160\text{e}+01 \pm 4.353\text{e}+00$

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